

**THE MEDIATING ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON THE RELATIONSHIP
BETWEEN VOCABULARY KNOWLEDGE AND WRITING
SKILLS AMONG ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS:
A QUANTITATIVE STUDY**

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The Mediating Role of Social Media on the Relationship Between Vocabulary Knowledge and Writing Skills among English Major Students: A Quantitative Study

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Abstract

Social media plays a significant role in our daily life. It also serves as more than just a means of sharing and connecting, to influence on people's lives in variety of ways, including education. Hence, the purpose of this study was to determine the mediating role of social media in the relationship of vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. Quantitative non-experimental research utilizing descriptive correlational technique and mediation analysis were utilized in the study. The data were gathered from 214 English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology through inclusion and exclusion criteria. Findings revealed that the level of social media was high; and the levels of vocabulary knowledge and writing skills were also high. There were positive significant relationships between vocabulary knowledge, writing skills, and social media. Moreover, result also revealed that social media was partially mediated, or it has a significant role in the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skill. It signifies that the teachers should look into other factors that is affecting vocabulary knowledge of a student and not just their writing skills. Perhaps, teachers should also consider social media as it partially mediated or significantly affect the relationship of vocabulary knowledge and writing skills.

Keywords: *English major student, social media, vocabulary knowledge, writing skills, mediation analysis*

Introduction

Writing is a crucial language skill for conveying information, transactions, and emotions, but mastering it, especially in a second language, is a complex and challenging endeavor. However, at all educational levels, spanning from elementary to secondary and, surprisingly, even in higher education, a significant number of students encounter multiple challenges when it comes to writing. Writing is particularly difficult for students in elementary and secondary school because they have weak vocabulary and poor reading comprehension. As a result, the person moves from ignorance to knowledge. It illustrates the purpose of writing because a man who cannot read or write is referred to as being illiterate and ignorant (Eka, 2018; Khan, 2020).

In Malaysia, in learning writing skills students encountered several challenges as follows; limited vocabulary, poor grammatical structure, spelling difficulties, limited access to books, and low motivation. Therefore, such challenges prevent students from making progress in writing good quality output. To these challenges arising there is the need by the educators to know the problems faced by both learner and teacher together with the use of the most efficient teaching techniques such as feedback and forwarding (Moses & Mohamad, 2019).

In the Philippines, a research shows that writing challenges are as prevalent as in lower classes, and continue to the college and university levels. Student challenges include demoralization, time unavailability, less practice, poor feedback, fewer resources, numerous students in a class, ineffective teaching techniques, and origin. Performance in writing is reduced by eight areas of weakness, articles, agreements, tenses, pronouns, prepositions, vocabulary usage, spelling and singular/plural confusion. (Ramos, 2019).

This study is timely and relevant, as students today face diverse forms of writing particularly in the academic field. Also, having this study is relevant to student's education as this could give valuable information that would give new perspective with regards to the mediating effect of social media on the relationship of vocabulary knowledge and writing skills of students particularly to where the study is conducted. The findings have the potential to offer a fresh perspective, serving as a foundation for educators and the educational sector to consider the effective integration of social media as a teaching and learning tool based on the study's outcomes. Therefore, this study shows social relevance by carefully examining the contributions it offers to society in general. It emphasizes the practical role in the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills in digital age.

Moreover, there have been prior studies entitled "Utilizing Social Media in Improving Creative Writing Skills of Grade 7 Students in English" by Pagaras & Francisco (2020) and "Social Media and It's Influence on Vocabulary and Language Learning: Case Study" by Zainal & Rahmat (2020). However, none of them had investigated the mediating role of social media on the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills among English major students, as this study does. The previous studies focus in improving creative skills in younger students and examining the influence of social media on vocabulary and language learning. In contrast, my research investigates the quantitative mediating role of social media in the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills among English major students. The purpose is to develop a deeper understanding of this into the role of social media in enhancing vocabulary knowledge and writing skills in English majors.

The research findings of this study will be shared with relevant stakeholders, partners, academic institutions, community members by sharing copies of research papers, reports or summaries and publication in research journals and conference presentation. The aim of

this dissemination plan is to distribute it to key stakeholders, enabling them to engage actively with significant research findings. The researcher aims to enhance the significance and relevance of the research within a scientific, collaborative, and community setting by circulating printed copies of the research article.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was determined whether social media significantly mediates the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills of English major students. To be specific, the study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of:
 - 1.1. proficiency;
 - 1.2. ability; and
 - 1.3. concentration.
2. To describe the level of writing skills in terms of:
 - 2.1. attitudes towards writing;
 - 2.2. generating;
 - 2.3. revising;
 - 2.4. feedback; and
 - 2.5. awareness and control of writing process.
3. To describe the level of social media in terms of:
 - 3.1. students addictiveness;
 - 3.2. exposure of students to social media; and
 - 3.3. use of social media.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. vocabulary knowledge and writing skills;
 - 4.2. vocabulary knowledge and social media; and
 - 4.3. social media and writing skills.
5. Is there a mediating effect of Social Media on the relationship of Vocabulary Knowledge and Writing Skills?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive-correlational and mediation analysis quantitative research design. This implied that the study observed how the social media variable affects the students based on their vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. Quantitative research involves use of figures and figures analyzed to give out features such as frequency, average or increase and is the overall opposite of qualitative research which is based on use of nonnumeric data. Such type of research can be used to generate hypothesis, examine causality and make prediction on extended populations (Bhandari, 2020).

In the context of the study, a quantitative research methodology was adopted for this investigation because it was permitted the measurement and analysis of numerical data, which were crucial for discovering patterns, making predictions, and evaluating causal correlations between variables. In addition, the utilization of descriptive-correlational research design was facilitated the exploration of the relationships between vocabulary knowledge, writing skills and social media among the research participants. Lastly, the results were generalized to a larger population enabled by the application of statistical analysis, which were raise the study's outward consistency. Consequently, it was appropriate to adopt a quantitative research strategy for this study since it was provided a comprehensive examination of the relationships between the factors of interest in an organized and impartial manner.

Moreover, descriptive correlational research is designed to describe the relationship of more than two variables without implying that one causes the other. This study design involves data gathering and analysis on such variables with the aim of determining the possibility of existence of a relationship between such variables. Descriptive correlational research helps researchers understand factors and their relationships without altering them or assuming causality, aiming to provide a comprehensive explanation without altering variables. In addition, descriptive correlational research focuses on understanding how different factors relate without determining cause and effect. Researchers observe and measure these factors, looking for patterns and connections within the data. Unlike experimental research, which manipulates variables, this method simply describes and analyzes existing relationships. By examining how variables interact, researchers can identify potential connections and trends within a population (Bhat, 2023).

In this study, a quantitative descriptive-correlational design was employed to investigate the relationship between vocabulary knowledge, writing skills, and social media use among English major students. This research approach was chosen to determine how social media might influence the connection between vocabulary and writing abilities. In simple words, mediation analysis signifies the addition of the third variable to $X \rightarrow Y$ relation, where X causes the mediator M , and Y , so $X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$ (MacKinnon et al., 2014).

A mediating variable (M) is an intervening variable that is at the centre of the interaction between an independent variable (X) and a dependent variable (Y). They assist in defining the nature of the relationship between them As well as the causal process that relates

them. In mediated relationship, when the independent variable affects the mediating variable, the mediating variable affects the dependent variable. These variables are also known as post or intermediate variables owing to their placement in the causal sequence (MacKinnon, 2001).

In this study, the mediating role of social media in the relationship between vocabulary knowledge as an independent variable, writing skills as dependent variable and social media acts as a mediating variable. Hence, social media as a mediating factor affects vocabulary knowledge and the development of writing skills, highlighting its importance as a mediator that shapes the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skill in that academic context.

Respondents

The respondents of this study involved English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST) during the second semester of AY: 2023-2024. The study focused on examining the relationship between social media, vocabulary knowledge, and writing skills among English major students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST). To ensure a representative sample, Slovin's formula was employed to calculate the sample size based on a desired margin of error. English major students were included in the study, while those from other academic programs or institutions were excluded. This selection process aimed to maintain the relevance of the research within the specific academic context. By applying inclusion and exclusion criteria randomly, the study sought to make sure that it was fair and accurate, and that it followed good scientific practices.

The population was divided into subcategories called strata in stratified random sampling where each stratum was chosen using uniform random sampling. In this case, the strata are the four sections of first year college education students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. The table 1 shows the distribution of the population of this study (Nguyen et al., 2020).

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

Track	Population	Sample	Percentage
1st Year	223	104	22.85%
2nd Year	136	64	13.94%
3rd Year	69	32	7.07%
4th Year	29	14	2.97%
Total	457	214	46.83%

Instrument

The researcher used the adopted questionnaires both on the independent, dependent and mediating variable that suits to the content of the study. The first set of questionnaires assessed with the level of Vocabulary Knowledge with three indicators with the total number of 15 items which adopted from the study of Balbuena (2022) that had the reliability test of (0.70). On the other hand, this set of questionnaires is

assessed with the level of Writing Skills with five indicators with the total number of 25 items which adopted from the study of Elbow & Belanoff (1989) that had reliability test of (0.85). And the third set of questionnaires assessed with the level of Social Media with three indicators with the total number of 15 items which adopted from the study of Peter (2015) that had the reliability test of (0.65).

The vocabulary knowledge questionnaire had three domains: proficiency with five items, ability with five items and concentration with five items.

The writing skills questionnaire had five domains: attitudes towards writing with five items, generating with five items, revising with five items, feedback with five items, and awareness and control of writing process with five items.

The social media questionnaire had three domains: students' addictiveness to social network and academic background with five items, exposure of students to social media network and their academic performance with five items, and use of social media and students' academic performance.

Procedure

In gathering data, the researcher observed the following steps in order to gather the data that needed for the study.

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. Prior to conducting the study, the researcher sent a letter of permission to the vice-president of academic affairs, requesting permission to conduct the study at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. As a result, the researcher also sought authorization from the Program Head of the Education Department. Afterward, the researcher requested the list and number of students, particularly the English major students, for the Academic Year 2023-2024, from the Office of the Registrar.

Orientation of the Respondents. Upon the approval, the researcher coordinated the class mayors from the seven sections of English major students. The guidelines and ways of answering the questionnaire are aforementioned during the orientation. The researcher oriented the respondents in regards with the type of questionnaire.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. Upon the orientation of the respondents, the survey questionnaire was given to the respondents through their class mayors. At the time, the researcher monitored the number of respondents who had responded. If the respondents answered and most of them disregarded the questionnaire, the researcher would initiate ways to contact the respondents who had not responded yet. As the respondents completely answered the questionnaires, the researcher retrieved the questionnaires.

Collection and Tabulation of Data. The research instruments were checked and gathered together for the tabulation of the data. During the tabulation of the data, the researcher experienced difficulties in tabulating the data since there were 214 respondents.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools was used to calculate the data of this study at a 0.05 level of significance:

Mean. This was used to determine the level of mediating effect of social media on the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills.

Pearson r. This was used to determine the relationship between social media, vocabulary knowledge and writing performance.

Medgraph using Path analysis. This was used to utilized and to analyze the level of mediation among variables. This type of test is intended for the measurement of mediation effect of a variable on the relationship between the independent and dependent variable.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of this study were all English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. In this case, the researcher ensured that the safety, rights, and trust of the participants in the study was respected and protected, and that the study's purpose is carried out with integrity and fairness.

To ensure the sound conduct of the study, ethical considerations were addressed and considered accordingly. These considerations were the informed consent, the risk of harm, anonymity and confidentiality, and the conflict of the interest (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011; Berg & Lune, 2017). The first core aspect of ethical considerations is how to address informed consent. Participants was well-informed about the goals, procedures, and potential outcomes (if any). Participants was provided unambiguous, positive, and signed consent to participate in the study. Participants was aware of their ability to access their information and cancel consent at any moment. Participants and researchers can view the consent procedure as a contract (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

During the informed consent process, the respondents were oriented on the following rights that they had. The respondents informed that they had the right to terminate participation without any need of explanation. They also had the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. Another right that they had was the entitlement to ask questions about the study. Lastly, they also had the rights to informed of the study results after this research is accomplished.

Risk of Harm, Maintaining Confidentiality, and Anonymity is the second core principles of ethical considerations. It pertains to the protection of a study participant so that not even the researcher can link the participants with the data provided, as well as the avoidance of disclosing the participant's identity to anybody other than authorized individuals (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Furthermore, the selective disclosure of data poses a significant risk of harm. Prioritizing participant safety and confidentiality, this study adhered to the Data Privacy

Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173) to protect individual personal data. To safeguard participant anonymity, all identifying information was removed from the dataset, stored securely, and deleted after three years. Data was collected and used solely for the purpose of this study.

Conflicts of Interest is the third core aspect of ethical considerations. It recognizes the existing relationships or previous activities by the researcher could result in conflict of interest, which must be transparently revealed in an ethics approval application so the committee can provide advise on how to address the conflict.

Additionally, it occurs when a person prioritizes their personal interests or commitments over their responsibilities as a researcher, or is perceived to prioritize them over their duties and responsibilities. Conflicts of interest may be actual, hypothetical, or perceived and may involve incentives in money or in nonmonetary rewards. Conflicts of interest may impair a researcher's objectivity and judgment, or may perceived to affect, which undermines the reliability of the findings (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Therefore, as the study participants were students, external factors impacting the research results were minimal. The researcher remained impartial throughout the study, free from any potential to influence participants. Conflict of interest arises when researchers can exert pressure or manipulate participants' involvement.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings and results on the mediating role of social media on the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing performance of first year college student. Analyses and interpretations of data were done parallel to the research objectives.

Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Proficiency

The level of vocabulary knowledge of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator proficiency. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 are the mean scores of the respondents' responses on their level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of proficiency. The data revealed that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of proficiency had a total mean of 3.84 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of proficiency was oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.91 was obtained from item no. 3 - Knowing which words are important to me to learn with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.85 was obtained from item no. 1 - Reading many reading materials to enhance my vocabulary with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Table 2. *Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Proficiency*

	<i>Proficiency</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	reading many reading materials to enhance my vocabulary.	3.85	High
2.	repeating the new word orally several times.	3.87	High
3.	knowing which words are important for me to learn.	3.91	High
4.	reviewing my vocabulary regularly to reinforce retention and enhance language proficiency.	3.71	High
5.	guessing the meaning of new word using background knowledge and the immediate and the wider context.	3.86	High
	Overall	3.84	High

Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Ability

The level of vocabulary knowledge of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator ability. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 3 are the mean scores of ability. The data revealed that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of ability had a total mean of 3.81 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of vocabulary knowledge was oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.91 which was obtained from item no. 1 - Finding my own way of learning new words with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.84 was obtained from item no. 4 – Using common sense and knowledge of word when guessing the meaning of word with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Table 3. *Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Ability*

	<i>Ability</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	finding my own way of learning new words.	3.91	High
2.	having a plan of accumulating words.	3.73	High
3.	using vocabulary section or glosses in my textbook to learn new words.	3.65	High
4.	using common sense and knowledge of word when guessing the meaning of word.	3.84	High
5.	creating mental images of the words i learn.	3.90	High
	Overall	3.81	High

Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Concentration

The level of vocabulary knowledge of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator concentration. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 4. *Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Concentration*

	<i>Concentration</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	paying attention to the pronunciation of a new word.	4.22	High
2.	extending and improving my ability to concentrate for longer periods of time in checking the meaning of new words in dictionaries.	3.94	High
3.	ensuring the accurate spelling of newly written words by giving careful attention and repetition.	4.07	High
4.	focusing only on the words that is much difficult to understand.	3.71	High
5.	limiting my social media usage enhances my concentration during academic activities.	3.60	High
	Overall	3.91	High

Presented in Table 4 are the mean scores of concentration. The data revealed that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of concentration had a total mean of 3.91 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of concentration was oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.22 was obtained from item no. 1 - Paying attention to the pronunciation of a new word with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the English major students.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.60 was obtained from item no. 5 – Limiting my social media usage enhances my concentration during academic activities with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Summary on the Level of Vocabulary Knowledge

The data on the level of vocabulary knowledge of English major students was reflected in Table 5. Revealed in table 5, the overall mean score was 3.85, or described as high. This indicates that the level of vocabulary knowledge was oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

It was observed in the table that the indicator, concentration, got the highest mean of 3.91, or was described as high. This indicates that the indicator concentration is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

The indicator, ability, got the lowest mean score of 3.81, or was described as high. This indicates that the indicator ability is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

The indicator, proficiency, got the mean of 3.84, or described as high. This indicates that the indicator proficiency is oftentimes manifested by English major students.

Table 5. *Summary Level of Vocabulary Knowledge*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Proficiency	3.84	High
Ability	3.81	High
Concentration	3.91	High
Total	3.85	High

Level of Writing Skills in terms of Attitudes Towards Writing

The level of writing skills of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator Attitudes Towards Writing. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 6 are the mean scores of attitudes towards writing. The data revealed that the level of writing skills in terms of attitudes towards writing had a total mean of 3.83 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of writing skills in terms of attitudes towards writing was oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.94 was obtained from item no. 3 – Considering writing to be valuable skill in both academic and professional context with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Table 6. *Level of Writing Skills in terms of Attitudes Towards Writing*

<i>Attitudes Towards Writing</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	finding act of writing to be enjoyable and fulfilling.	3.91	High
2.	exploring different writing styles to enhance my skills.	3.77	High
3.	considering writing to be a valuable skill in both academic and professional contexts.	3.94	High
4.	feeling assured about my capability to effectively convey my thoughts through writing.	3.71	High
5.	trusting myself as a person who can find good words, ideas, and perception.	3.80	High
Overall		3.83	High

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.71 was obtained from item no. 4 – Feeling assured about my capability to effectively convey my thoughts through writing with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Level of Writing Skills in terms of Generating

The level of writing skills of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator Generating. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 7 are the mean scores of generating. The data revealed that the level of writing skills in terms of generating had a

total mean of 3.57 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of writing skills in terms of generating was oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.79 was obtained from item no. 5 – Seeking inspiration and diverse sources to generate ideas in writing with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.49 was obtained from no. 1 – Generating multiple words quickly without constraints item with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Table 7. Level of Writing Skills in terms of Generating

	<i>Generating</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	generating multiple words quickly without constraints.	3.49	High
2.	generating ideas or insight that not thought before.	3.47	High
3.	feeling confident in my ability to generate creative ideas for writing.	3.50	High
4.	enjoying the process of brainstorming and generating ideas before starting to write.	3.63	High
5.	seeking inspiration and diverse sources to generate ideas in writing.	3.79	High
	Overall	3.57	High

Level of Writing Skills in terms of Revising

The level of Writing Skills of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator Revising. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 8 are the mean scores of revising. The data revealed that the level of writing skills in terms of revising had a total mean of 3.68 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of writing skills in terms of revising was oftentimes manifested.

Table 8. Level of Writing Skills in terms in Revising

	<i>Revising</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	identifying the primary idea in a disorganized piece of writing.	3.74	High
2.	predicting the likely reactions of most readers to my written work.	3.63	High
3.	acknowledging that skillful revising plays a substantial role in enhancing the overall quality of my writing.	3.66	High
4.	taking satisfaction in thoroughly revising and polishing my writing to achieve perfection.	3.64	High
5.	recognizing the revising process as an essential step in enhancing the clarity and coherence of my writing.	3.75	High
	Overall	3.68	High

The highest mean is 3.75 was obtained from item no. 5 – Recognizing the revising process as an essential step in enhancing the clarity and coherence of my writing with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.63 was obtained from item no. 2 –Predicting the likely reactions of most readers to my written work with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Level of Writing Skills in terms of Feedback

The level of Writing Skills of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator Feedback. The responses of the respondents on each indicator was presented and analyzed below. Presented in Table 9 are the mean scores of feedback. The data revealed that the level of writing skills in terms of feedback had a total mean of 3.94 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of writing skills in terms of feedback was oftentimes manifested.

Table 9. Level of Writing Skills in terms of Feedback

	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	valuing receiving feedback on my writing helps me identify areas for improvement.	4.07	Very High
2.	seeking my peers' feedback and understanding how well they comprehend my writing.	3.91	High
3.	believing that feedback play a crucial role in enhancing the overall quality of my writing.	3.98	High
4.	actively seek feedback from others to gain different perspectives on my writing.	3.89	High
5.	perceiving control over the writing process as a key factor in achieving my writing goals.	3.84	High
	Overall	3.94	High

The highest mean is 4.07 was obtained from item no. 1 – Valuing receiving feedback on my writing helps me identify areas for improvement with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the English major students

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.84 was obtained from item no. 5 – Perceiving control over the writing process as a key factor in achieving my writing goals with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Level of Writing Skills in terms of Awareness and Control of writing Process

The level of Writing Skills of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator Awareness and Control of Writing Process. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 10 are the mean scores of awareness and control of writing process. The data revealed that the level of writing skills in terms of awareness had a total mean of 3.93 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of writing skills in terms of awareness and control of writing process was oftentimes manifested.

Table 10. *Level of Awareness and Control of Writing Process*

<i>Awareness and Control of Writing Process</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	believing that being aware of my writing strengths and weaknesses is essential for improvement.	4.09	Very High
2.	trying to open different strategies to improve my control over the writing process.	3.90	High
3.	assessing regularly and adjust my writing approach based on the specific requirements of the task.	3.86	High
4.	planning actively and organize my writing tasks before starting the actual composition.	3.91	High
5.	having perceive control over the writing process as a key factor in achieving my writing goals.	3.90	High
Overall		3.93	High

The highest mean is 4.09 was obtained from item no. 1 – Believing that being aware of my writing strengths and weaknesses is essential for improvement with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the English major students.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.86 was obtained from item no. 3 – Assessing regularly and adjust my writing approach based on the specific requirements of the task with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Summary Level of Writing Skills

The data on the level of writing skills of English major students was shown in Table 11. Revealed in table 11 the overall mean score of 3.79, or described as high. This indicates that the level of writing skills was oftentimes manifested.

It was observed in the table that the indicator, feedback, got the highest mean score of 3.94, or was described as high. This indicates that the indicator feedback is oftentimes by the English major students.

The indicator, generating, got the lowest mean score of 3.57, or was described as high. This indicates that the indicator generating is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Table 11. *Summary Level of Writing Skills*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Attitudes towards writing	3.83	High
Generating	3.57	High
Revising	3.68	High
Feedback	3.94	High
Awareness and control of writing process	3.93	High
Total	3.79	High

The indicator awareness and control of writing process got the mean score of 3.93, or was described as high. This indicates that the indicator awareness and control of writing process is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

The indicator attitudes towards writing got the mean score of 3.83, or described as high. This indicates that the indicator attitudes towards writing is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

The indicator revising got the mean score of 3.68, or described as high. This indicates that the indicator revising is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Level of Social Media in terms of Student Addictiveness to Social Network and Academic Performance

The level of social media of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator Student Addictiveness to Social Network and Academic Performance. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 12 are the mean scores of student addictiveness to social network and academic performance. The data revealed that the level of social media in terms of student addictiveness to social network and academic performance had a total mean of 3.62 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of writing skills in terms of student addictiveness to social network and academic performance was oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.82 was obtained from item no. 1 – Finding addiction to social networks poses a significant challenge that impacts my academic performance with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.20 was obtained from item no. 4 – Finding that there is no improvement in my grades since I engaged in social media sites with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Table 12. *Level of Social Media in terms of Student Addictiveness to Social Network and Academic Performance*

	<i>Students Addictiveness to Social Network and Academic Performance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	finding addiction to social networks poses a significant challenge that impacts my academic performance.	3.82	High
2.	finding online social networks distracting in my studies.	3.73	High
3.	spending hours online that can never be compared to the numbers of hours i spend in writing/reading.	3.64	High
4.	finding that there is no improvement in my grades since i engaged in social media sites.	3.20	High
5.	believing that social media addiction can hinder my ability to concentrate on my academic responsibilities.	3.70	High
	Overall	3.62	High

Level of Social Media in term of Exposure to Social Media Networks and their Academic Performance

The level of social media of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator Exposure of Students to Social Media Networks and their Academic Performance. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 13 are the mean scores of exposures of students to social media networks and their academic performance. The data revealed that the level of social media in terms of exposure of students to social media networks and their academic performance had a total mean of 3.36 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the level of writing skills in terms of exposure of students to social media networks and their academic performance was sometimes manifested.

Table 13. *Level of Social Media in term of Exposure to Social Media Networks and their Academic Performance*

	<i>Exposure of Students to Social Media Networks and their Academic Performance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	having unlimited access to facebook and this has affect my academic performance negatively.	3.50	High
2.	engaging in academic discussions on twitter and this has improve my academic performance.	3.01	Moderate
3.	making use of messenger to disseminate knowledge to my classmate.	3.59	High
4.	relying solely on information gotten from wikipedia to do my assignment without consulting other sources.	2.99	Moderate
5.	being aware of the various social media platforms that i use regularly.	3.72	High
	Overall	3.36	Moderate

The highest mean is 3.72 was obtained from item no. 5 – Being aware of the various social media platforms that I use regularly with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. In contrast, the lowest mean is 2.99 was obtained from item no. 4 – Relying solely on information gotten from Wikipedia to do my assignment without consulting other sources with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This means that the item is sometimes manifested by the English major students.

Level of Social Media in term of Use of social Media and Students Academic Performance

The level of social media of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator Use of Social Media and Students Academic Performance. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 14 are the mean scores of used of social media and students' academic performance. The data revealed that the level of social media in terms of use of social media and students' academic performance had a total mean of 3.72 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of social media in terms of use of social media and students' academic performance was oftentimes manifested.

Table 14. *Level of Social Media in term of Use of Social Media and Students Academic Performance*

<i>Use of Social Media and Students Academic Performance</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Using google for research to helped me improve my grades.	3.90	High
2.	Engaging in academic forums on social media.	3.50	High
3.	Using materials gotten from blogging sites to complement what I have been taught in class	3.49	High
4.	Being aware of the potential distractions caused by social media and their impact on my study habits.	3.81	High
5.	Believing that social media can serve as a valuable educational tool if used responsibly.	3.90	High
Overall		3.72	High

The highest mean is 3.90 was obtained from item no. 5 – Believing that social media can serve as a valuable educational tool if used responsibly and no. 1- Using google for research to helped me improve my grades with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the items are oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.49 was obtained from item no. 3 – Using materials gotten from blogging sites to complement what I have been taught in class with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested

Summary Level of Social Media

The data on the level of social media use by English major students is illustrated in Table 15. Table 15 showed the overall mean score 3.57, which was described as high. This indicates that the level of social media was oftentimes manifested.

It was observed in the table that the indicator, use of social media and student's academic performance, got the highest mean score of 3.72, or was described as high. This indicates that the indicator use of social media is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

The indicator, exposure to social media networks and their academic .821r (214) = .821, indicating a very strong positive relationship. The p-value is less performance, got the lowest mean score of 3.36, or was described as moderate. This indicates that the indicator exposure of students to social media is sometimes manifested of the English major students.

Table 15. *Summary Level of Social Media*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Student Addictiveness	3.62	High
Exposure Of Students To Social Media	3.36	Moderate
Use Of Social Media	3.72	High
Total	3.57	High

The indicator, student addictiveness, got the mean score or 3.62, or was described as high. This indicates that the indicator student addictiveness is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Correlation between Vocabulary Knowledge and Writing Skills

Presented in Table 16, the correlation between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills among English major students in English language with, $r(214) = .821$, $p < .001$. At 0.05 level of significance.

As a result, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing performance among English major students is rejected in this context. This stipulates that there is a positive high significant relationship between the two variables with 82% of the variation between the 2 variables. This indicates that a high level of vocabulary knowledge is the better writing with fine expression. Those English major students who are familiar with many words then can express their ideas within the written language more effectively than those English major students who are acquainted with few words. Consequently, expanding and strengthening the amount of word knowledge through direct instruction along with reading can become a fruitful way toward enhancing the writing abilities of students.

Furthermore, in table 16, the correlation between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills among English major students shows a correlation coefficient $r(214) = .821$, $r(214) = .821$, indicating a very strong positive relationship. The p-value is less than .001, which is significantly below the 0.05 level of significance. Given this p-value, the null hypothesis was rejected which it is hypothesized that there is no relationship between the two variables. The findings provide evidence that the high coefficient found is not attributable to a sampling error and strengthens the second hypothesis under investigation, that is, vocabulary knowledge is positively associated with

writing skills of the students.

Table 16. *Correlation between Vocabulary Knowledge and Writing Performance*

Variables	Mean	R-value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Vocabulary Knowledge	3.85			
Writing Skills	3.79	0.821	<.001	Ho Rejected

Correlation between Vocabulary Knowledge and Social Media

Presented in Table 17, the correlation between vocabulary knowledge and social media among English major students in English language, $r(214) = .462$, $p < .001$. At 0.05 level of significance.

For that reason, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between vocabulary knowledge and social media is rejected in this context. This entails that there is a positive moderate significant relationship between the two variables with 46% of the variation between the 2 variables. This indicates that a high level of vocabulary knowledge as for lexical features, the students who have developed their strong vocabulary through the use of social networks with a high concentration toward enhancing their lexical proficiency are capable of writing regarding more complicated ideas and complicated concepts than their peers.

Consequently, in table 17, the correlation between vocabulary knowledge and social media usage among English major students is $r(214) = .462$, $r(214) = .462$, indicating a moderate positive relationship. The p-value is less than .001, which is significantly below the 0.05 level of significance. Given this very low p-value, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that the analysis shows that the correlation of the results are not likely to have happened by chance differing from probability. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected and accept the alternative hypothesis that, there is a significant relationship between the students' Vocabulary knowledge and social media usage among the English major students.

Table 17. *Correlation between Vocabulary Knowledge and Social Media*

Variables	Mean	R-value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Vocabulary Knowledge	3.85			
Social Media	3.57	0.462	<.001	Ho Rejected

Correlation between Social Media and Writing Skills

Presented in Table 18, the correlation between social media and writing skills among English major students in English language, $r(214) = .485$, $p < .001$. At 0.05 level of significance.

Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between social media and writing skills is rejected in this context. The above-mentioned data presented, stipulates that there is a positive moderate significant relationship between the two variables with 48% of the variation between the 2 variables. This indicates that the use of social networks in particular, often and adequately developed, is associated with better writing skills. Students who spend time on different social media outlets take time to form meaningful posts and comments then can write more effectively in written work than students who rarely use social media. As a result, forcing and directing students to engage in social forums as well as showing them how to produce effective social making posts could be one of the effective methods to enhance the overall writing abilities students have in any setting. Writing short captivating copy for the target social media groups sharpens writing skills.

Consequently, in table 18, the correlation between social media usage and writing skills among English major students is $r(214) = .485$, $r(214) = .485$, indicating a moderate positive relationship. The p-value is less than .001, which is significantly below the 0.05 level of significance. Given this very low p-value, the null hypothesis was rejected which it is hypothesized that there is no relationship between the variables. This statistically significant result indicates that the observed correlation is unlikely to have occurred by chance. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a meaningful association between social media usage and writing skills among the students.

Table 18. *Correlation between Social Media and Writing Performance*

Variables	Mean	R-value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Social Media	3.57			
Writing Skills	3.79	0.485	<.001	Ho Rejected

Mediation Analysis

The approach used in mediation analysis is based on Preacher and Hayes, who focused on the indirect effect. In this approach, two types of mediation are considered: partial mediation and full mediation. According to partial mediation, indirect and direct effects from X to Y are expected to be significant. Thus, the unmediated relationship is significant, as the X to mediator and mediator to Y

relationships. In full mediation, the mediator does not need to be present for X to have a large direct impact on Y.

Direct Effect. The direct effect becomes minimal in the presence of the mediator, but the indirect effect becomes significant. Otherwise, the mediation process will not occur if there are negligible relationships between the mediator and X or the mediator and Y.

It can be observed in Table 19 the direct effect of affective vocabulary table 19 knowledge (IV) on writing skills (DV). The result revealed that vocabulary knowledge directly and significantly affects writing skills, (B=0.651, SE=0.037, 95% CI [0.579, 0.723]).

Table 19. *Direct Effect*

		95% Confidence Interval				
		Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	Lower Upper
IV --->	DV	0.651	0.037	17.635	<.001	0.579 0.723

In addition to the statement based on the data presented that, it is also observed that every unit increased in the independent variable, vocabulary knowledge will entice 0.651 increase in the dependent variable, writing skills. This signifies that the independent variable is significantly influencing the dependent variable which is the writing skills. This implies that the vocabulary knowledge has a direct effect on writing skills and that as the vocabulary knowledge increases, writing skills increases as well. Furthermore, this relationship underscores vocabulary knowledge was found to be highly correlated to the writing skills, hence, good knowledge of words directly leads to good writing. In particular, the link between the development of vocabulary knowledge as a student and development of their writing skills will be positive.

Indirect Effect. It can be noticed in Table 20 the indirect effect of vocabulary knowledge (IV) on social media (MV) and on writing skills (DV). The result revealed that social media partially mediated the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills, (B=0.053, SE=0.018, 95% CI [0.017, 0.090]).

Furthermore, it can be perceived that every unit increased in the independent variable will entice 0.053 increase to the dependent variable as it goes through the which is the social media, the independent variable, vocabulary knowledge is still mediating variable which is much lesser compared to the unit increase in table 20 which is 0.651. This announces that even in the presence of the mediating variable which is the social media, the independent variable, vocabulary knowledge is still significantly influencing the dependent variable which is writing skills. Since social media is a mediator variable, this implies that vocabulary knowledge has an indirect effect on social media. As vocabulary knowledge, so does writing skills, even when social media is present.

Table 20. *Indirect Effects*

		95% Confidence Interval				
		Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	Lower Upper
IV --->	MV ---> DV	0.053	0.018	2.896	0.004	0.017 0.090

Total Effects. It can be observed in Table 21 the total effects of vocabulary knowledge (IV) on writing skills (DV). The result revealed that the total effect of vocabulary knowledge in both direct and indirect effect towards writing skills is significant, (B=0.704, SE=0.033, 95% CI [0.639, 0.770]).

Also, as shown in the results, it could be inferred that in every unit increased in the independent variable, vocabulary knowledge, will entice 0.702 increases to the dependent variable, writing skills. This means that the independent variable, vocabulary knowledge, is significantly influencing the dependent variable which is the writing skills. This implies the total effect of the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills, in which as vocabulary knowledge increases, the increase of writing skills is also significantly influenced.

Table 21. *Total Effects*

		95% Confidence Interval				
		Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	Lower Upper
Table 21	Table 21	Table 21	Table 21	Table 21	Table 21	Table 21

Conclusions

The foregoing results can be concluded, thus:

English major students demonstrate a high sense of vocabulary knowledge. This reveals that the respondents had given importance and significant importance in enriching their vocabulary knowledge of English major students in terms in of proficiency, ability, and concentration. English major students emphasize the expansion of Vocabulary list showing high level of proficiency, ability, and focused concentration.

Subsequently, the respondents perform at a high level concerning writing skills in answers to the questions posed. This means in terms of the English major student’s writing capabilities, dispositions towards writing, generation, revision, the feedback process, as well as an understanding and management of the English language lexicon. Further, it proves their knowledge or lack of it in English language

practice and the learning process.

The respondents also reveal considerable active usage of social media. This means that the English major students have now adapted to social media in as much as their addiction, exposure and usage frequency is concerned in terms of students addictiveness, exposure of students to social media, and use social media. This points to a possibility of better learning outcomes since the students are already familiar with social media and may be acquainted with skillful uses of the same in teaching practices.

Moreover, there is a significant relationship among the three variables: vocabulary knowledge and writing skills; social media and writing skills; and vocabulary knowledge and social media, which were tested in this study and in which the null hypothesis was rejected.

On top of that, the mediation analysis reveals that social media has partially mediated or significantly affected the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. Therefore, along with developing students' knowledge about a certain topic, a classroom teacher ought to incorporate social media. It could help to revolve education to be more interesting and closer to the society we are living in today

Findings of the study revealed that vocabulary knowledge, writing skills and social media is generally high among the English major students. The level of independent variable which was the vocabulary knowledge in terms of its indicators was high. The dependent variable which was the writing skills in terms of its indicators the level was also high among the respondents. Also, the mediating variable which was the social media, with its indicators revealed was high too.

Therefore, social media was significantly mediating the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. This study suggested that the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and Department of Education (DepEd) may consider creating initiatives for training teachers or conducting workshops to further enhance the skills of teachers in advancing the degree of using social media. For teachers, they might consider participating in any trainings, workshops, or seminars for them to be equipped with skills and other ways to integrate social media in the classroom, as it was found to be a high or significant predictor of the writing skills of students. Students should consider not only their vocabulary knowledge, but also how they engage with and use social media correctly, as this may affect their writing skills.

As a result, students should know the benefits of using social media for boosting their knowledge and skills, including vocabulary and writing activity. Teachers should maintain full awareness of present and developing development in use of technology specifically in social media, and be in a position to incorporate the development in teaching methods. Thus, it is also proposed that in future studies, other variables that may mediate the relationship between the two variables, namely vocabulary comprehension, should be investigated.

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